

Deliverable D5.2: First report on MAX training events

D5.2

First report on MAX training events

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Due date of deliverable: 31/12/2024 (month 24)
Actual submission date: 30/12/2024
Final version: 23/12/2024

Lead beneficiary: CNR (participant number 1)
Dissemination level: PU - Public

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Document information

Project acronym: MAX
Project full title: Materials Design at the Exascale
Research Action Project type: Centres of Excellence for HPC applications
EC Grant agreement no.: 101093374
Project starting / end date: 01/01/2023 (month 1) / 31/12/2026 (month 48)
Website: www.max-centre.eu
Deliverable No.: D 5.2

Authors: Daniele Varsano, Maria Bartolacelli, Susanna Cavicchioli, and Luisa Neri

To be cited as: D. Varsano et al., (2024): First report on MAX training events. Deliverable D5.2 of the HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01 project MAX (final version as of 23/12/2024). EC grant agreement no: 101093374, CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche.

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Versioning and contribution history:

Version	Date	Author	Note
1	27/11/2024	Susanna Cavicchioli and Maria Bartolacelli	First draft
2	06/12/2024	Daniele Varsano	Revision and Implementation
3	23/12/2024	Luisa Neri	Final version

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List of abbreviations

NCC	National Competence Centre
CoE	Centre of Excellence
WP	Work Package
HPC	High-Performance Computing
DFT	Density Functional Theory
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
BSE	Bethe-Salpeter equation
MBPT	Many-Body Perturbation Theory
NEGF	Non-Equilibrium Green's Function
JU	Joint Undertaking
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Development
QE	Quantum ESPRESSO

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.2 provides a comprehensive overview of the education and training activities carried out within the MaX project in the first two years of the project, highlighting user participation, involvement, and the impact of these initiatives. Building on the structured Training and Education Plan proposed in D5.1, MaX has successfully implemented a domain-specific program at a pan-European level, aiming to foster a new generation of skilled developers and proficient code users. The plan outlined strategies to reach a wide and diverse community by leveraging collaborations with National Competence Centres (NCCs) and renowned organizations such as CECAM, Psi-k, and ICTP.

In these early 24 months of the project, significant progress has been made in implementing the plan through a variety of actions, including:

- **Organization of 12 training schools**, with 5 additional events scheduled for the near future. These schools, dedicated to MaX flagship code users, emphasized practical skills with extensive hands-on sessions and addressed challenges related to the usage of codes on pre-exascale machines.
- **Organization of 3 hackathons and workshops**, designed to train a new generation of developers, focusing on advancing MaX codes and adapting them for cutting-edge HPC infrastructures.
- **Collaborations with academic programs**, contributing to 8 Master and PhD curricula by providing introductory courses on computational materials science, hands-on training on MaX flagship codes, and best practices for their use in HPC environments.
- **Hosting researchers in MaX labs**, where participants received tailored training, ranging from basic introductions to specialized training on MaX codes development.
- **Active participation in external training events**, with MaX experts contributing to schools and workshops organized by NCCs and other Centres of Excellence (CoEs).

A major outcome of these efforts is the creation of a rich library of training materials, including tutorials and video lectures. These resources have been published on the dedicated training platform, **Lhumos**, ensuring accessibility to the broader community and enhancing the sustainability of the training initiatives.

The extensive collaborations with NCCs, research institutions, and CoEs have been instrumental in achieving MaX training objectives, enabling a diverse array of participants to engage with its educational offerings.

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The partners responsible for the implementation of this work package include CNR, SISSA, ICN2, FZJ, CEA, UBREMEN, CINECA, BSC, IT4I, IJS, ATOS, SIPEARL, and LEONARDO.

2 Structure and Team behind WP5

Thanks to experience gained in the previous project phases, MaX is today able to offer a wide range of training opportunities. Many collaborations have been set up in the past years, and specific working groups have been organised to flank the WP Leader in planning, defining, and implementing the activities of the WP. Furthermore, there is a continuous effort to evaluate and refine the training program and adapt it to the evolving needs of the computational materials science community.

WP5 “Training and community engagement” is structured in the following way:

1. The **WP5 Training Team**, led by Daniele Varsano, and composed by Maria Bartolacelli, Susanna Cavicchioli, and Luisa Neri (CNR), is in charge of the management of the overall training activities;
2. A dedicated **Training Working Group** hosts representatives from each active node involved in training activities. It is composed of: Daniele Varsano (CNR; chair), Alice Ruini (UNIMORE), Oscar Baseggio (SISSA), José María Escartín Esteban (ICN2), Alberto García (CSIC), Gregor Michalicek (FZJ), Cristiano Malica (UBREMEN), Laura Bellentani (CINECA), Julio Gutiérrez (BSC), Karina Pesatova (IT4I), Tone Kokalj (IJS).
3. A **Hackathon Working Group**, coordinated by Oscar Baseggio (SISSA) gathers code developers and experts from supercomputing centres, and is focused on organizing hackathons to train young code developers in accordance with the activities of WP1-3. The Hackathon committee is formed by Daniele Varsano (CNR), Andrea Ferretti (CNR), Oscar Baseggio (SISSA; chair), Stefano De Gironcoli (SISSA), Daniel Wortmann (FZJ), Luigi Genovese (CEA), Alberto Garcia (CSIC), Federico Pedron (ICN2), Fabio Affinito (CINECA), Lubomir Riha (IT4I), Ondřej Vysocký (IT4I).

2 Training offered by MaX

As outlined in the *Training and Education program* (D5.1, M6), MaX has developed diverse training formats to meet the needs of various audiences. All events follow the guidelines specified in Annex 1 of D5.1, focusing on equity, inclusion, and the effective dissemination of training materials. Additionally, participant statistics and user feedback are collected to support

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continuous improvement. Many events have been organized in collaboration with the European HPC ecosystem, fostering partnerships and enhancing the program impact.

2.1 Events and actions dedicated to supporting and expanding the users base of MAX codes: Specialized schools and hands-on tutorials

In the first two years, MaX organized a series of specialized schools and hands-on tutorials aimed at training young scientists from academia and industry on the best practices and efficient usage of MaX flagship codes in high-performance computing (HPC) environments. These events combined theoretical lectures on the codes' underlying algorithms and methods with practical sessions focused on code usage, parallel computing, memory management, and performance optimization techniques.

Participants gained hands-on experience through guided exercises using state-of-the-art HPC machines acquiring essential HPC skills, such as parallel computations, efficient memory management, and techniques for optimizing performance and scalability. The workshops typically lasted 3 to 5 working days with flexible formats (in person, online, and hybrid setups) meant to meet the growing demand for training. In several cases hands-on sessions made use of Virtual Machines containing code executable and hands-on training material. This setup ensures a smooth learning experience as the software pre-installation on the participant machines is no longer required.

A total of 12 events (Tab. 1) were conducted: dedicated to specific flagship codes (e.g., Events 1-4) or covering multiple codes (e.g., Events 5-6). Details on events, including organizing partners, participant statistics, feedback summaries, and training materials, are provided in Annex 1. All events were effectively promoted through social media banners (see D6.2), mailing lists, newsletters, code fora. Importantly, they were uploaded to the HPC Training Portal¹, the portal for European HPC services, to ensure wide visibility and accessibility.

To expand its outreach and impact, MaX collaborated with renowned organizations in the computational materials science community, such as CECAM, Psi-k, and ICTP. Additionally, several events were co-organized with NCCs across Europe, fostering a broader engagement within the EuroHPC ecosystem. These specialized workshops allowed participants to stay updated on the latest advancements in computational materials science while acquiring essential HPC skills.

¹ <https://hpc-portal.eu/>

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Training events organized by MaX, focused on lighthouse codes		
No.	Event Title	Venue
1	Ab-initio many-body perturbation theory: from equilibrium to time-resolved spectroscopies and nonlinear optic (Yambo)	Rome (IT)
2	All electron DFT with Fleur - a Hands-on Tutorial	Juelich (DE)
3	Advanced Quantum ESPRESSO school: Hubbard and Koopmans functionals from linear response	Pavia (IT)
4	First steps with SIESTA: from zero to hero	Online
5	Yambo-Aiida plugin tutorial	Online
6	Efficient materials modelling on HPC with Quantum ESPRESSO, SIESTA, and Yambo	Online
7	Machine Learning Modalities for Material Science	Ljubljana (SI)
8	PWTK-2024: An Online Tutorial	Online
9	MaX school: Materials and molecular modelling with Quantum ESPRESSO	Online
10	Fleur Hands-on Tutorial 2024	Online
11	MaX/HPC-NCC-Croatia QE workshop (Modelling of (nano)materials with Quantum ESPRESSO)	Zagreb (KR)
12	SIESTA School 2024	Online

Table.1: List of schools and hands-on workshops on MaX Flagship code organized in 2023-2024. Detailed information about each event is provided in Annex 1.

In addition to the 12 events organized by the CoE, MaX partners shared their expertise at numerous events hosted by other institutions, delivering lectures and tutorials on MaX flagship codes. These collaborations involved key organizations within the EuroHPC ecosystem, including NCCs, HPC centres, and other CoEs. Table 2 highlights key contributions where MaX partners provided training and support on the flagship codes. Furthermore, MaX partners were invited to

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offer training at international events outside Europe, as detailed in Table 3, underscoring the global significance of MaX flagship codes and the ongoing need for specialized training in their use.

Training provided by MaX partners in events promoted by other European organizations			
Date	Event	People	Partner/Code
07/06/2023	Numerical Methods in Quantum Chemistry, Thromso (Norway). Tutorial ²	L.Genovese T. Deutsch	CEA BigDFT
02/08/2023 10/08/2023	“High-performance electronic-structure calculations in the exascale era” at “How Exciting! 2023” workshop. Humboldt University, Berlin, DE. Event sponsored by the NOMAD CoE. ³	J. Gutierrez	BSC
13-17/11/2023	TranSIESTA School 2023 Lyngby (DK) ⁴	ICN2	ICN2
27-28/11/2023	Quantum Espresso: Application for material science and chemistry, Evora (PT) ⁵ . In collaboration with EuroCC2	A. Ferretti	CNR Quantum ESPRESSO
01/12/2023	OpenMP Offloaded Quantum ESPRESSO, online tutoring ⁶	L. Bellentani F. Ferrari Ruffino	CINECA CNR
29/01/2024 - 02/02/2024	Virtual Winter School in Computational Chemistry ⁷	L. Genovese	CEA BigDFT
03/09/2024 - 04/09/2024	Materials modelling at the atomic scale: Hands-on on ab-initio calculation on Siesta. Istinye University Istanbul Turkey	J. Gutierrez	BSC Siesta

Table.2: List of schools and hands-on workshops organized by other Institutions of the EuroHPC ecosystems as CoE, HPC Centres and Universities where MaX partners provided training on MaX flagship codes

² <https://mrchemsoft.no/nmqc-2023/>

³ <https://www.exciting-code.org/how-exciting-2023/howx23-welcome>

⁴ https://siesta-project.org/siesta/events/TranSIESTA_School-2023/

⁵ <https://indico.hpc.uevora.pt/event/65/>

⁶ <https://www.openmp.org/wp-content/uploads/OMP-seminar.pdf>

⁷ <https://winterschool.cc/>

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Training provided on MaX codes in events organized outside of Europe			
Date	Event	People	Partner/Code
12/06/2023 -23/06/2023	7th African School on Electronic Structure Methods and Application: Tutorial. Kigali (RWA). ⁸	A. Marini	CNR Yambo
20/02/2023 24/02/2023	Regional African School on Electronic Structure Methods and Applications” (RASESMA): Organisation and tutoring. Nairobi (KEN). ⁹	A. Marini and D. Varsano	CNR Yambo
13/06/2023- 16/06/2023	1st African Summer School on Molecular Modelling. Training activity. Kenitra (MAR). ¹⁰	A. Slassi	CNR
04/12/2023 06/12/2023	Teaching at Workshop on Novel Methods for Electronic Structure Calculations. Trends in software for electronic structure. La Plata (ARG). ¹¹	P. Giannozzi	CNR Quantum ESPRESSO
10/06/2024 - 16/06/2024	School on Electron-Phonon Physics, from First Principle. Austin, TX (USA). ¹²	P. Giannozzi	CNR - QE
12/10/2024- 26/10/2024	Workshop on High Performance Computing for Materials Characterization, Design and Discovery. Barranquilla (COL). ¹³	A. Marini	CNR Yambo

Table.3: List of schools and hands-on workshops organized by other Institutions outside the EuroHPC ecosystem.

2.2 Events and actions dedicated to training new generations of developers: Hackathons and coding events

To ensure comprehensive training for the next generation of developers, MaX adopted the hackathon format, enabling participants to gain hands-on experience through direct interaction with leading code developers, HPC experts, and industry specialists. These events fostered collaboration among new developers, principal developers of MaX codes, external contributors, and HPC programming and accelerator technology experts.

⁸ <https://indico.ictp.it/event/10181>

⁹ https://wiki.yambo-code.eu/wiki/index.php/RASESMA_2023_Nairobi

¹⁰ <https://fs.uit.ac.ma/premiere-ecole-dete-africaine-en-modelisation-moleculaire/>

¹¹ <https://congresos.unlp.edu.ar/xwnmesc/wp-content/uploads/sites/71/2023/09/Giannozzi.pdf>

¹² <https://ashpc.eu/event/23/>

¹³ <https://indico.ictp.it/event/10504/overview%7C>

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The planning and organization of these specialized events were managed by a dedicated committee of flagship code developers and staff of HPC centres. In 2023-2024, MaX hosted three hackathons: two focused on GPU optimization, involving experts from major GPU card and compiler vendors such as Intel, AMD, and NVIDIA, targeting specific flagship codes. The third event addressed multiple codes, concentrating on mini-app extraction for testing libraries and components of MaX codes, alongside discussions on automating CI/CD processes for mini-apps across all HPC MaX centres. Detailed descriptions of these events are provided in Annex 2.

Additionally, MaX partners participated as tutors and lecturers in cross-disciplinary hackathons and coding events organized by other institutions. Drawing on their experience with MaX codes, they provided training to both emerging and experienced developers. While their expertise was rooted in work on MaX codes, the primary focus of these events extended beyond MaX-specific advancements, emphasizing broader HPC and domain-specific development skills. A list of the most significant events is provided in Tab.4.

Training Contributions by MaX Partners in HPC Domains and Developer Outreach Organized by European Institutions				
No	Date	Event	People	Partner/Code
1	09/05/2023	Webinar: Jube as benchmarking tool	L. Bellentani	CINECA, IT
2	12/06/2023-14/06/2023	MPI and OPENMP in scientific software development (in collaboration with NCC Netherlands) ¹⁴	N. Spallanzani	CNR, IT
3	28/08/2023 01/09/2023	Co-Design methods for computational materials simulations at the exascale. (Invited highlight talk) at 5th NOMAD project meeting. Aalto University, Espoo (FIN)	J. Gutierrez	BSC, ES
4	27/10/2023	Tutoring activity at “Introduction to Leonardo HPC cluster, for users and developers”, CINECA, Bologna	L. Bellentani, N. Spallanzani	CINECA and CNR, IT

¹⁴ <https://eurocc-netherlands.nl/calendar/mpi-and-openmp-in-scientific-software-development/>

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Training Contributions by MaX Partners in HPC Domains and Developer Outreach Organized by European Institutions				
		(IT) ¹⁵		
5	04/12/2023	Best Practices for CernVM-FS in HPC (in collaboration with MultiXscale CoE) ¹⁶	Barbara Krasovec	IJS, SLO
6	05/12/2023	Streaming Optimised Scientific Software: an Introduction to EESSI (in collaboration with MultiXscale CoE) ¹⁷	Barbara Krasovec	IJS, SLO
7	07/01/2024 11/01/2024	“Exascale HPC & Co-Design: a perspective from ab initio atomistic modelling methods” (Invited highlight talk) at 6th NOMAD project meeting. Finnish IT Centre for Science, CSC, Kajaani (FIN)	Julio Gutierrez	BSC, IT
8	28/10/2024 - 31/10/2024	Nvidia GPU Hackathon Epicure event ¹⁸ . Tutoring	Laura Bellentani	CINECA, IT
9	05/10/2024	MPI and OPENMP in scientific software development ¹⁹ (in collaboration with NCC Netherlands)	Nicola Spallanzani	CNR, IT
<p>Table.4: List of events organized by other Institutions as CoEs, NCCs; HPC Centres and Hardware vendors where MaX partners provided training towards developers.</p>				

2.3 Training for visiting researchers

Hosting researchers in CoE labs has proven to be an effective training method throughout past phases of MaX. This approach engaged a wide range of participants, including PhD students, researchers, and software developers. Building on this success, MaX hosted **31 young researchers** during the first two years of the current project.

¹⁵ <https://eventi.cineca.it/en/hpc/introduction-leonardo-hpc-cluster-users-and-developers/bologna-20231027>

¹⁶ <https://event.ugent.be/registration/event/84b45c41-b98b-4a41-9aae-60f5f9e89440>

¹⁷ <https://event.ugent.be/registration/event/201863f3-cead-498b-9659-16d98c966eab>

¹⁸ <https://epicure-hpc.eu/2024/09/19/nvidia-gpu-hackathon/>

¹⁹ <https://www.surf.nl/en/agenda/mpi-and-openmp-in-scientific-software-development-0>

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The visits focused on various objectives depending on participants' needs. Many aimed to familiarize researchers with the functionalities of MaX flagship codes and the underlying theories applied in areas such as electronic, optical, and transport properties of materials, high-throughput computation, and data analysis. Others emphasized advanced training in developing new code features, designing workflows, and implementing porting strategies.

Overall, the training visits addressed three main goals: foundational training on flagship code usage, enabling independent execution of basic calculations; advanced training linked to specific research projects, fostering expertise in specialized simulations; and development-focused training for creating tools and libraries to extend the codes' capabilities for targeted scientific applications.

A detailed list of researchers, host institutions, and visit purposes is provided in Annex 3.

2.4 Training for Master, PhD and undergraduate students

MaX places a strong emphasis on training the next generation of scientists and developers by extending its educational efforts to Master and PhD students, as well as university instructors. Recognizing the importance of integrating cutting-edge computational methods into higher education, MaX has provided specialized courses, seminars, and flexible teaching modules centred on its flagship codes.

The training events offered by MaX include theoretical and hands-on sessions, to enable participants to gain a deep understanding of HPC-based computational modeling. Teaching modules were developed and tested in collaboration with academic institutions offering Master and PhD programs in HPC-related fields, such as SISSA, UNIMORE, RWTH Aachen, and Oviedo University, and leveraging established partnerships like the SISSA/ICTP Master in High Performance Computing.

This comprehensive approach ensures that MaX computational expertise is effectively integrated into university programs, fostering a new generation of skilled researchers and professionals ready to face the challenges of HPC-driven scientific domains. A list of the courses designed, developed, and taught by MaX partners is detailed in Table 6.

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In addition to MaX participation in Master/PhD programs, MaX partner institutions have hosted and supported 31 PhD students who have either completed or are currently pursuing their doctoral studies in MaX labs. Through these research experiences, the students have acquired advanced skills in both the use and development of MaX codes, contributing directly to the advancement of the MaX codes and extending their capabilities. The technical expertise gained by these students in HPC and computational modeling is invaluable for their future careers, whether in academia or industry, where these skills are increasingly in demand for solving complex scientific and engineering challenges.

The list of the trained PhD students is given in Annex 4.

Contribution of MaX partners in Master/PhD courses			
Date	Course	People	Partner
Academic Years 2022-2024	Design and tutoring activity in the “Laboratory of Quantum Simulation of Materials” at master-level university class on electronic structure methods, focus on density functional theory (DFT) including Hands-on in HPC, organised by University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (IT).	A. Ruini, A. Ferretti, and D. Varsano	CNR and UNIMORE, IT
Academic Years 2022-2023	Contribution to the Master program of the RWTH Aachen University (DE) on electronic structure methods, focus on density functional theory (DFT).	S. Bluegel	FZJ, DE
Academic Years 2023-2024	Contribution to the M. Sci program in Physics joint between Trieste and Udine Universities (IT) “Numerical Methods for Electronic Structure”.	P. Giannozzi	CNR, IT
Academic Years 2022-2023	PhD course at Jozef Stefan Institute (SLO) “Molecular modeling using density functional theory: molecules, surfaces, and bulk solids”.	A. Kokalj	IJS, SLO
04/2023	“Atomistic computational materials simulations” (guest lecturer) and “Atomic level computational materials	J. Gutierrez	BSC, ES

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Contribution of MaX partners in Master/PhD courses			
	modelling in the exascale era” Simulation of Materials and Nanostructures course of the M.Sc. in Advanced Physics. Uni Oviedo (ES).		
04/2023	“Computational modelling of fusion materials at the atomic scale” (guest lecturer) in the Fusion Technology course of the Nuclear Engineering M.Sc. Polytechnic University of Catalonia (ES).	J. Gutierrez	BSC, ES
02/2024	Hands-on for PhD program in Mathematics and Physics, Udine University (IT): “Classical and Quantum Simulations of nano- and bio-systems”	P. Giannozzi	CNR, IT
Academic Years 2022-2024	Contribution to the master program in Computational sciences at Faculty of Electronics and Engineering, University of Ostrava (CZ) with a specialisation in HPC. Courses on Introduction to HPC systems (including hand-on sessions) and Introduction to programming of HPC systems.	L. Říha, O. Vysocký	IT4I, CZ
06-07/2024	Lectures of First-Principles Simulations of Materials: Fundamentals and Applications to Nano-Electronics, Thermal Transport and Electrochemistry, PhD course in Nano and Physics PhD school, Univ. of Modena and Reggio Emilia (IT).	P. Ordejón	ICN2, ES
Academic Years 2022-2024	Contribution in the SISSA/ICTP Master in High Performance Computing with the courses: "Introduction on Quantum ESPRESSO" and “parallel GPU programming”, Trieste (IT).	S. De Gironcoli P. Delugas	SISSA, IT

Table.5: List of contributions of MaX Partners in Master/PhD program providing training for undergraduate students in topics related with MaX CoE.

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2.5 Coordination and contributions to transverse training initiatives

This task encompasses MaX coordination and contributions to cross-domain training initiatives within the European HPC ecosystem through its domain-specific expertise. It involves collaboration with key stakeholders, including NCCs, HPC centres, other CoEs, and EuroHPC Training Activities and Professional Traineeships funded by the Digital Europe Programme.

The primary focus is on delivering domain-specific content, enhancing software development know-how for exascale systems, and integrating cutting-edge knowledge into university education. Core activities include:

- Collaborating with NCCs, HPC centres, and other CoEs on courses and training initiatives.
- Contributing to training portals and CASTIEL2 CSA training activities.
- Developing flexible teaching modules tailored to HPC and computational materials science.

Key Actions Undertaken:

- Uploaded all MaX training events to the HPC Training Portal.
- Actively participated in CASTIEL2 “Training Coffee Break” meetings held monthly since May 4, 2023.
- Presented “MaX Training: Plan and Strategies” at the CASTIEL2 “Training Coffee Break” on October 5, 2023 [D. Varsano, CNR].
- Contributed to the EuroCC & CASTIEL2 "Training Sprint Initiative" with three events (Events 9, 11, and 12 in Annex 1).
- Coordinated with NCCs for three additional training events focused on MaX flagship codes (Events 6, 7, and 8 in Annex 1).
- Contributed in 2 training activities for developers in collaboration with NCCs (Events 2,9 in Tab. 5)
- Contributed in 4 training events for developers in collaboration with other CoE (Events 3,5,6,7 in Tab.5)

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3 Participants statistics and considerations for future activities

This section provides a detailed analysis of participation in MaX training events over the first 24 months of the project. Key metrics such as the number of participants, their countries of origin, gender distribution, and institutional affiliations are examined. The statistics reflect the broad impact and diversity of MaX educational initiatives while offering valuable insights for shaping future training activities.

During this period, MaX organized 15 training events focused on equipping young researchers with knowledge, skills, and best practices related to MaX flagship codes (Annex 1), along with specialized training for code developers (Annex 2). Half of these events were conducted in collaboration with NCCs, and collectively more than **850 young researchers** were trained. Considering the varying durations of the events, the total training delivered amounts to **3,934 person-days**, with 1,075 person-days in 2023 and 2,839 in 2024 (+164%).

Chart 1: Pie chart showing the distribution of MaX training events (2023-2024): 50% held in person and 50% online, reflecting MaX's commitment to accessibility and diverse participation

The interest in MaX training offerings is evidenced by **nearly 1,200 applications** received in total. Due to logistical constraints, it was not always possible to accept all applicants. To address these challenges and ensure broader access, **50% of the events were held in person, while the remaining 50% took place online**. This balanced approach highlights MaX commitment to accommodating diverse participation preferences while maximizing accessibility.

Additionally, all lectures from both in-person and online events were recorded and made available alongside the training materials produced during the events (see Section 3.7), ensuring long-term access and ongoing learning opportunities. We believe that combining in-person and online formats offers an optimal training experience. In-person events are particularly valuable for advanced topics, where direct interaction with expert developers and tutors fosters deeper learning. Meanwhile, online sessions allow for broader participation, especially for introductory training aimed at new users of MaX flagship codes. This dual approach has proven effective, and we plan to continue this format in the next years.

Approximately 75% of participants in MaX events came from European countries, with the remaining 25% from outside Europe, primarily India, the US, China, and Brazil. Chart 2 (right)

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illustrates the distribution of European participants, highlighting a non-negligible representation from Eastern Europe (19% of the total number of participants). This is partly attributable to events organized directly in Eastern European countries or in collaboration with their NCCs (Events 7-9,11 in Annex 1).

Participant feedback from MaX training events has been overwhelmingly positive. Based on anonymous feedback forms, the events received an impressive average satisfaction score of 4.5 out of 5. The evaluation scale ranged from 1 (“very poor”) to 5 (“excellent”), reflecting high participant approval. This strong rating underscores the effectiveness of MaX training approach. Chart 3 illustrates the satisfaction levels reported for each training event, showcasing consistently high evaluations across the entire program.

Chart 3: Participant Satisfaction Levels for MaX Schools Based on Anonymous Feedback Surveys

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Within the pool of participants, **26.7% were women**, while women delivering training (as tutors and lecturers for hands-on sessions) accounted for **17.0%**. MaX is aware of the **gender imbalance** that persists and is actively working to address it.

The user base in the field of HPC and computational sciences already suffers from a gender imbalance, which MaX is committed to addressing: “Data from 2018 European research show that, at European level, women continue to be under-represented among Doctoral graduates in the narrow STEM fields of Physical Sciences (38.4%), Mathematics & Statistics (32.5%), ICT (20.8%), Engineering & Engineering Trades (27%), and Architecture & Construction (37.2%)”, according to European report *She Figures 2021*²⁰. To this end, several actions have been implemented. For example, 40% of the fellowships for the "Computational School on Electronic Excitations in Novel Materials" (Trieste, January 2020) were awarded to women. MaX is also actively promoting applications from female candidates through targeted channels, including networks for young women and women professors. Social media campaigns, where women make up 42% of the audience, have been used to further raise awareness and encourage female participation. In addition to this effort, MaX launched initiatives to raise the visibility of women in science (see D7.2), including a social media campaign for the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

Chart 5: Gender distribution of Lectures and Tutors in MaX training events

Despite these efforts, the statistics show that more work is needed. MaX is committed to fixing this imbalance, particularly by increasing female involvement in event organization and among invited lecturers. The project aims to ensure gender-balanced representation in future training events and will continuously refine its approach based on measurable impacts, such as participant numbers, gender representation, and feedback.

Chart 4: Gender distribution of participants in MaX training events

²⁰ European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2021 : gender in research and innovation : statistics and indicators*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090>

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The **provenance** of participants in MaX training activities reveals that a significant majority, 97%, came from academia, while only 3% were from industry (in spite of the initiatives organized jointly with NCCs). This disparity highlights that, although the format of the MaX schools has proven to be highly attractive to the academic audience, it has not been as appealing to the industrial sector, which, according to our experience, tend to select different approaches, notably including for-pay ad hoc training.

To bridge this gap, MaX is exploring alternative formats and strategies to better engage industrial users, such as targeted outreach initiatives, industry-focused events emphasizing relevant applications, and further enhanced collaborations with NCCs. Among the first steps, MaX training team has held a dedicated meeting with NCC Italy members, identifying strategies for industrial engagement.

4 Availability of high-quality educational materials

Over the past two years, MaX, in collaboration with other European organizations such as CECAM (Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire), has been actively involved in developing the **Lhumos platform** (www.alpha.lhumos.org).

Lhumos is a modern, interactive training environment that makes available educational resources related to computational materials science and HPC. It is a centralized hub for video lectures, tutorials, and specialized training modules, making advanced knowledge accessible to a broad audience.

One of its key features is a *user-centric design* offering a structured and intuitive interface for learners of various expertise levels. The platform's modular organization allows users to follow comprehensive learning paths or explore specific topics at their convenience, ensuring that both early-career researchers and seasoned professionals can benefit.

Fig.1: Images from Lhumos platform.

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By leveraging cutting-edge web technologies, Lhumos enhances the visibility and impact of MaX educational initiatives, ensuring that its extensive repository of training materials reaches a global audience.

Lhumos is almost ready, and the platform is expected to be fully operational by early March 2025. Its launch will be announced through a dedicated webinar. In the meantime, the alpha version (<https://alpha.lhumos.org/>), available since early 2024, is attracting considerable interest, and the MaX channel has already received about 500 visits.

5 Planned events and KPIs

Building on the training plan and best practices established during the initial phase, MaX remains dedicated to delivering high-quality training events. A series of workshops, tutorials, and training sessions have already been scheduled, ensuring a seamless continuation of knowledge transfer and skill development..

The main features of upcoming events will be kept alike to those of the past: the focus will be on strengthening domain-specific expertise in HPC-based computational materials science and related fields, and granting access to as many interested participants as possible with in-person and online formats. Scheduled events include:

- **Advanced SIESTA Workshop 2025** – Barcelona (ES), June 2025 (in collaboration with Psi-k)
- **Use-case Tutorial on Materials Modeling on HPC Machines** – Ljubljana (SI), 2025 (in collaboration with Slovenian NCC)
- **School on Machine Learning for Molecules and Materials Research** – Zadar (KR), 9-13 June 2025 (in collaboration with Psi-k)
- **SIESTA School 2025** – Online, Fall 2025
- **Excited States in Complex Materials by MBPT Methods** – Modena (IT), May 2025 (in collaboration with Psi-k).

The high number of applications received in 2023-2024 stresses the ongoing need for training events in the research community. This strengthens our confidence that upcoming events will gain wide interest from researchers and developers eager to acquire or enhance their expertise in computational materials science and MaX flagship codes within the HPC environment.

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To measure the effectiveness and impact of the MaX training efforts, specific **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** have been established for MaX’s training and education tasks. The target and the current status of these KPI are reported in Table 7.

KPI no.	KPI definition		M12	M18	M24	M30	M36	M42	M48
K5.1	Number of people trained in MAX training events (in terms of person-training days)	Target	750	1130	1500	1880	2250	2630	3000
		Current	1075	2834	3934				
K5.2	Number of collaborative actions for the HPC ecosystem	Target	2	4	6	8	10	12	14
		Current	9	13	15				

Table.6: List of Training KPIs.

The data clearly demonstrates that the performance of MaX training and education activities has significantly exceeded the internal KPIs set in D7.3. Specifically, the **Number of people trained in MaX training events (K5.1)** and the **Number of collaborative actions for the HPC ecosystem (K5.2)** have exceeded initial targets by 162% and 150% respectively. The high number of participants and the MaX proactive approach in collaborating with NCCs, research institutions, and other CoEs underline the strong interest and demand for these training activities.

6 Conclusions

The activities managed by WP6 in Training and Community Engagement have been highly successful to date. The quantity and quality of events, the number of participants, and the wide range of topics covered clearly demonstrate how MaX long-term commitment to training users and developers is both well-established and finely tuned to meet the needs of the audience. Within the MaX consortium, nearly all partners and flagship code owners actively collaborate to deliver training initiatives, addressing a broad spectrum of expertise levels—from master’s students to senior researchers and developers. Furthermore, achieving the training goals relies heavily on the strong collaboration of WP5 with WP6 Communication and WP7 Management, particularly for the organizational and promotional aspects.

Moving forward, MaX aims at expanding its training offer, at fostering new collaborations, and at keeping the standards in quality and inclusivity.

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Annex 1: Fact sheet of training events on MaX flagship codes.

Event No. 1 Ab-initio many-body perturbation theory: from equilibrium to time-resolved spectroscopies and nonlinear optic		Logo and Codes: 	
Website: https://www.yambo-code.eu/2023/02/18/yambo-school-2023/			
Venue and Dates: Rome (Italy) 22-26/05/2023	Partners: 	In collaboration with:	
Organizers: D. Varsano (CNR), F. Paleari (CNR), D. Sangalli (CNR), M. Grüning (Queen's University Belfast), M. Palummo (University of Rome Tor Vergata), and A. Molina-Sánchez (University Of Valencia)			
Summary: The school focused on many-body perturbation theory approaches for first-principles simulations of excited states in materials using the YAMBO code. Advanced nonequilibrium techniques for ultrafast spectroscopy were also covered with the CHEERS code. Participants attended theoretical and technical lectures, complemented by hands-on sessions applying the codes to realistic simulations in the HPC environment. Core topics included quasiparticles through the GW approximation and excitons via the Bethe-Salpeter equation. Advanced discussions explored nonlinear optics and time-resolved dissipative dynamics using nonequilibrium Green's function theory. Each topic was introduced with relevant experimental contexts and clear connections to the practical exercises.			
Applicants: 88 Participants: 39 (29M / 10F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire 4.64/5.0.			
Notes:			

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The training material is available:

Tutorials: https://wiki.yambo-code.eu/wiki/index.php/Rome_2023**Videlectures:** <https://alpha.lhumos.org/spaces/2>

Event No. 2		Logo and Codes:	
All electron DFT with Fleur - a Hands-on Tutorial			
Website: https://www.cecaml.org/workshop-details/1226			
Venue and Dates: Juelich (Germany) 8-12/05/2023	Partners: 		
Organizers: D. Wortmann (FZJ), S. Bluegel (FZJ), and G. Michalicek (FZJ)			
Summary: The school offered comprehensive training on Density Functional Theory (DFT) and the full-potential linearized augmented-plane-wave (FLAPW) method, with a focus on their practical applications. Designed for researchers and practitioners, the event aimed to enhance participants' understanding of these methods for predicting the electronic, magnetic, and structural properties of materials. Through the sessions, attendees gained advanced insights into the role of DFT and FLAPW in materials screening and development. Additionally, the event fostered valuable interactions between users and developers, promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange. The hands-on part of the school was based on the FLAPW code FLEUR, the GW approximation code FLEUR-Spex, and AiiDA together with the AiiDA-FLEUR plugin.			
Applicants: 32 Participants: 11 (10M / 1F)			
Overall assessment: The participants' feedback has been overwhelmingly positive. The overall score from the anonymous feedback questionnaire was 5.0/5.0.			
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials: The tutorial is provided and continuously updated in a docker container openly available at https://www.flapw.de/MaX-7.0/tutorial_docker/ Videlectures: A growing collection of lecture videos from FLEUR tutorials is available at https://www.flapw.de/MaX-7.0/video/			

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<p>Event No. 3</p> <p>Advanced Quantum ESPRESSO school: Hubbard and Koopmans functionals from linear response</p>		<p>Logo and Codes:</p>
<p>Website: https://sites.google.com/view/hubbard-koopmans-2023/home?authuser=0</p>		
<p>Venue and Dates:</p> <p>Pavia (Italy) 28/8-01/09/2023</p>	<p>Partners:</p>	
<p>Organizers: A. Ferretti (CNR), M. Cococcioni (U. Pavia), N. Colonna (EPFL), and I. Timrov (PSI)</p>		
<p>Summary: The school successfully introduced PhD students, postdocs, and junior scientists to cutting-edge methods for modeling complex materials using first principles methods. The program covered the fundamentals of DFT and density-functional perturbation theory (DFPT), focusing on extended Hubbard and Koopmans functionals. These approaches address key limitations in standard DFT, enabling more accurate ground-state and spectral property predictions. Participants engaged in theoretical lectures, technical presentations, and hands-on sessions using Quantum ESPRESSO, gaining practical skills in computing Hubbard parameters and Koopmans screening coefficients. The event fostered a deeper understanding of advanced DFT methods and equipped attendees with tools for their research and educational activities.</p>		
<p>Applicants: 180 Participants: 41 (29M / 12F)</p>		

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Overall assessment: The feedback that was received from the participants has been overwhelmingly positive highlighting the engaging and interactive learning environment, the expertise of lecturers, and the valuable opportunity to explore new methods. Some proposals of improvement and suggestions about longer hands-on sessions, and school duration will be very valuable for shaping future editions of the school. Score: 8.5/10.

Notes:

The training material is available:

Tutorials: <https://github.com/materialscloud-org/QuantumESPRESSO-school-2023>

Videolectures: <https://alpha.lhumos.org/spaces/2>

A full report of the event can be found at:

<https://psi-k.net/advanced-quantum-esspresso-school-hubbard-and-koopmans-functionals-from-linear-response/>

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Event No. 4 First steps with SIESTA: from zero to hero	Logo and Codes: 	
Website: https://www.cecam.org/workshop-details/first-steps-with-siesta-from-zero-to-hero-1240		
Venue and Dates: Online 2-6/10/2023	Partners: <small>Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire</small>	
Organizers: S. Achilli (University of Milan), E. Artacho (CIC nanoGUNE and University of Cambridge), A. Cammarata (Czech Technical University In Prague), J.M. Escartín (ICN2), J. Gutiérrez (BSC), N. Papior (Technical University of Denmark), F.N. Pedron (ICN2), and M. Pruneda (CSIC)		
Summary: The School provided hands-on training on the SIESTA code. Researchers and students from various scientific disciplines, including materials science, chemistry, and nanoscience, participated to enhance their skills in computational materials research. The school covered essential theoretical foundations of DFT and practical sessions on using SIESTA effectively. Participants learned how to adjust the software's accuracy and computational cost. Training also included parallelization techniques, efficient solvers, and advanced features like quantum transport using the non-equilibrium Green's function (NEGF) approach. The event successfully equipped participants with the skills needed to perform advanced simulations and analyze results using pre- and post-processing tools.		
Applicants: 156 Participants: 119 (84M / 35F)		
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants was extremely positive, and some suggestions from the participants were incorporated in the subsequent training events. The overall score from the feedback questionnaire was 4.65/5.00.		
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials and slides of the presentations are available on: https://siesta-project.org/siesta/events/SIESTA_School-2023/Sessions.html		

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Event No. 5		Logo and Codes:	
Yambo-Aiida plugin tutorial			
Website:			
https://www.yambo-code.eu/2024/01/12/yamboaiida/			
Venue and Dates:	Partners:	In collaboration with:	
Online 27-29/02/2024			
Organizers: D. Varsano (CNR), D. Prezzi (CNR), F. Paleari (CNR), M. Bonacci (PSI), M. Bercx (PSI), and A. Marrazzo (University of Trieste)			
<p>Summary: The school provided in-depth training on automating many-body perturbation theory (MBPT) calculations beyond density functional theory (DFT). Participants explored efficient algorithms for GW and Bethe-Salpeter equation (BSE) simulations, including robust convergence procedures and a novel GW band interpolation method using maximally localized Wannier functions. Practical sessions focused on the Aiida platform, enabling automation of GW convergences and band interpolation tasks. By the program's end, attendees had acquired the skills needed to advance materials discovery through state-of-the-art computational techniques.</p>			
Applicants: 66			
Participants: 32 (23M / 9F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire 4.8/5.0			
Notes:			
The training material is available:			
Tutorials , slides of the presentations and a dedicated version of the quantum mobile are available at: https://www.yambo-code.eu/2024/01/12/yamboaiida/			

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Event No. 6 Efficient materials modelling on HPC with QUANTUM ESPRESSO, SIESTA and Yambo		Logo and Codes: 	
Website: https://enccs.se/events/2024-03-efficient-materials-modelling-on-hpc/			
Venue and Dates: Online 11-15/03/2024	Partners: 		
Organizers: D. Varsano (CNR) and T. Wikfeldt (ENCCS)			
Summary: In this workshop, participants learned to run common calculations such as SCF, phonons, quasi-particle energies, and time-dependent properties using Quantum ESPRESSO, Yambo, and SIESTA. They gained hands-on experience preparing input files and interpreting output files to extract relevant material properties. The program also covered efficient use of HPC resources, focusing on data distribution schemes like plane waves, pools, and images. Participants explored parallelization and acceleration techniques, including MPI, OpenMP, and GPU-offload, as implemented in Quantum ESPRESSO, SIESTA, and Yambo.			
Applicants: 118 Participants: 78 (53M / 25F)			
Overall assessment: The participants' feedback has been extremely positive, reflecting a high level of satisfaction with the workshop's content. Suggestions provided will be considered for future improvements. Score from the anonymous feedback questionnaire: 4.22 /5.0.			
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials: https://enccs.github.io/max-coe-workshop/ Videolectures: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL2GgY1xUzfDm9jE90sDPdYeh_B3kj-ij			

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Event No. 7		Logo and Codes:	
Machine Learning Modalities for Material Science		 Machine Learning Modalities for Materials Science, 2024	
Website: https://ml4ms.ijs.si/			
Venue and Dates:	Partners:	In collaboration with:	
Ljubljana (Slovenia) 13-17/05/2024			
Organizers: S. Džeroski, (Jožef Stefan Institute), S. de Gironcoli (SISSA), P. Rinke (Aalto University), K. Rossi (TU Delft), S. Stevanoska (Jožef Stefan Institute), and M. Todorovic (University of Turku)			
Summary: Machine learning methods are transforming materials design, though they often underutilize data from diverse sources and modalities. This workshop aimed to address this gap by providing young researchers with a comprehensive overview of advanced machine-learning techniques for tackling key challenges in materials discovery. Participants explored strategies for integrating different types of information into a unified framework for materials design. The program featured invited talks, contributed presentations, and panel discussions focused on multi-modal, multi-objective, and multi-fidelity machine learning methods. This interactive format encouraged collaborative thinking and the development of innovative approaches in materials science.			
Applicants: 204 Participants: 132 (97M / 35F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire: 4.62/5.0			
Notes: The training material is available: Videlectures and slides of the presentations are available at: https://ml4ms.ijs.si/recordings/			

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Event No. 8 PWTk-2024: An Online Tutorial		Logo and Codes: 	
Website: http://pwtk.ijs.si/pwtk-2024.html			
Venue and Dates: Online 20-24/05/2024	Partners: 		
Organizers: A. Kokalj (IJS)			
Summary: The PWTk-2024 online tutorial aimed to teach participants how to automate Quantum ESPRESSO calculations using the PWTk scripting environment. The program covered topics from basic scripting to advanced workflow creation, enabling users to employ built-in functionalities or develop custom scripts. The tutorial featured daily hands-on sessions, allowing participants to practice on their laptops or desktops with access to an HPC supercomputer.			
Applicants: 152 Participants: 95 (71M / 24F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire: 4.77/5.0			
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials: https://repo.sling.si/tonek/PWTk-2024 Videlectures: http://pwtk.ijs.si/pwtk-2024.html			

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Event No. 9 MaX school: Materials and molecular modelling with QUANTUM ESPRESSO		Logo and Codes: 	
Website: https://events.it4i.cz/event/252/			
Venue and Dates: Online 18-21/06/2024	Partners: 		
Organizers: O. Baseggio (SISSA) and K. Pesatova (IT4I, NCC Czechia)			
Summary: The course provided a comprehensive curriculum covering the primary features of the QUANTUM ESPRESSO code, balancing theoretical concepts with practical applications. Designed for beginners and intermediate users, it offered hands-on training aimed at developing essential skills for using the code in research and academic projects. Participants with backgrounds in condensed matter physics or chemistry learned key aspects such as code compilation, basic scripting, and parallelization strategies, enabling them to perform simulations effectively and interpret computational results.			
Applicants: 201 Participants: 46 (32M / 14F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire 4.85/5.0			
Notes: The training material is available: Videolectures: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HknPIJzMmx0			

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Event No. 10 Fleur Hands-on Tutorial 2024		Logo and Codes:
Website: https://www.flapw.de/MaX-6.0/handson/		
Venue and Dates: Online 16-20/09 /2024	Partners: 	
Organizers: D. Wortmann (FZJ), S. Bluegel (FZJ), and G. Michalicek (FZJ)		
Summary: The 2024 FLEUR hands-on tutorial was held online from September 16th to 20th, offering an interactive learning experience for both new and experienced users of the FLEUR code. Each day featured morning talks on various FLEUR-related topics, followed by hands-on sessions where participants could apply their knowledge, interact with developers, and discuss challenges. The sessions were scheduled at different times to accommodate participants from various time zones. Additionally, a poster session provided an opportunity for participants to present their results and engage with the community.		
Applicants: 47 Participants: 47 (40M / 7F)		
Overall assessment: The participants' feedback has been overwhelmingly positive. Overall score from the anonymous feedback questionnaire: 4.42/5.0.		
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials: The tutorial is provided and continuously updated in a docker container openly available at https://www.flapw.de/MaX-7.0/tutorial_docker/ Videolectures: A growing collection of lecture videos from FLEUR tutorials is available at https://www.flapw.de/MaX-7.0/video/		

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Event No. 11		Logo and Codes:	
MaX/HPC-NCC-Croatia QE workshop (Modelling of (nano)materials with Quantum ESPRESSO)			
Website: https://www.hpc-cc.hr/NCC_Croatia_HPC_day_2024			
Venue and Dates:	Partners:	In collaboration with:	
Zagreb (Croatia) 12-13/11/2024			
Organizers: O. Baseggio (SISSA), A. Kokalj (IJS), M. Pobrežnik (IJS), and P. Delugas (SISSA)			
Summary: The workshop covered the key features of the Quantum ESPRESSO code, with an emphasis on developing practical skills in atomistic modeling using density functional theory methods. Participants gained hands-on experience applying these methods to real-world problems, focusing on practical applications. The goal was to equip attendees with the necessary skills to effectively use Quantum ESPRESSO on modern HPC systems in their research.			
Applicants: 10 Participants: 8 (7M / 1F)			
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and few suggestions from the participants help in further improving. Overall score from anonymous feedback questionnaire: 4.83/5.0			
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials: https://gitlab.com/kokalj/qe-workshop_ncc-croatia-2024 Videolectures:			

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Event No. 12 SIESTA School 2024	Logo and Codes:
Website: https://siesta-project.org/siesta/events/SIESTA_School-2024/	
Venue and Dates: Online 11-15/11/2024	Partners:
Organizers: C. Coll (ICN2), J.M. Escartín (ICN2), R. Farris (ICN2), J. Gutiérrez (BSC), F.N. Pedron (ICN2), and M. Pruneda (CSIC and ICN2).	
<p>Summary: The School provided hands-on training on the SIESTA code. Researchers and students from various scientific disciplines, including materials science, chemistry, and nanoscience, participated to enhance their skills in computational materials research. The school covered essential theoretical foundations of DFT and practical sessions on using SIESTA effectively. Participants learned how to adjust the software's accuracy and computational cost. Training also included parallelization techniques, efficient solvers, and advanced features like quantum transport using the non-equilibrium Green's function (NEGF) approach. The event successfully equipped participants with the skills needed to perform advanced simulations and analyze results using pre- and post-processing tools.</p>	
Applicants: 357 Participants: 151 (111M / 40F)	
Overall assessment: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive, and work has already started to adapt the next SIESTA school (scheduled for November 2025) to some of the suggestions they made. Overall score from the feedback questionnaire: 4.66/5.00.	
Notes: The training material is available: Tutorials and slides of the presentations are available on: https://siesta-project.org/siesta/events/SIESTA_School-2024/Sessions.html .	

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Annex 2: Fact sheet of MaX training events devoted to developers.

<p>Event No. 13</p> <p>Quantum espresso targeting accelerator</p> <p>Website: https://indico.ictp.it/event/10267/</p>		<p>Logo and Codes:</p>
<p>Venue and Dates:</p> <p>Trieste (Italy) 27-28/02/2023</p>	<p>Partners:</p>	
<p>Organizers: O. Baseggio (SISSA)</p>		
<p>Summary: The workshop combined training sessions with interactive discussions. It featured expert talks from major GPU card and compiler vendors, including Intel, AMD, and NVIDIA, alongside presentations from DevXlib developers. Developers shared their experiences highlighting key advancements in porting FFTXlib and challenges encountered in distributed linear algebra integration. Each session concluded with open discussions, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among participants..</p>		
<p>Participants: 18 (14M / 4F)</p>		

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Event No. 14 Hackathon on mini-app extraction and CI/CD Website: https://indico.ictp.it/event/10635/overview		Logo and Codes: 	
Venue and Dates: Trieste (Italy) 15-19/04/2024	Partners: 		
Organizers: O. Baseggio (SISSA) and the Hackathon team			
Summary: This hackathon aimed to develop and enhance mini-apps for testing libraries and components of MaX codes, as well as to reorganize and update the MaX mini-apps repository. During the event, participants defined common output formats and standardized documentation for the mini-apps. Additionally, discussions were held on automating CI/CD processes for the mini-apps across all HPC MaX centres. The hackathon also involved testing and applying protocols for translating Spack recipes to EasyBuild recipes.			
Participants: 20 (16M / 4F)			

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Event No. 15 Yambo Hackathon		Logo and Codes: 	
Website: https://www.yambo-code.eu/2024/11/15/yambo-developers-meeting-2024/			
Venue and Dates: Modena (Italy) 26-28/11/2024	Partners: 		
Organizers: D. Varsano (CNR), D. Sangalli (CNR), and A. Ferretti (CNR)			
<p>Summary: The Hackathon was organized through a combination of presentations, discussions, and coding sessions. The presentations covered key updates on Yambo's capabilities, including improvements in linear algebra, electron-phonon coupling, and real-time simulations. Updates on the Yambo-py platform, along with new features and ongoing projects related to machine learning techniques, were also presented by developers. The hackathon sessions focused on GPU porting, distributed GPU linear algebra, calculation of new observables (such as photoluminescence), and code maintenance, offering participants the opportunity to actively contribute to Yambo's development. The event concluded with a session dedicated to preparing the next release of the code.</p>			
Participants: 34 (25M / 9F)			

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Annex 3: List of researchers hosted in MaX labs

Surname	Name	Affiliation	Dates	Topic	MaX hosting unit	Host
Re Fiorentin	Michele	Politecnico di Torino, IT	05/03 - 05/05/23	Training calculation from first principle of luminescence spectra of two dimensional materials	CNR Nano	D. Varsano and F. Paleari
Qian	Tianxiang	Soochow University, CN	26/05 - 16/07/23	Training on the real-time module of the Yambo code	CNR ISM / Unimi	D. Sangalli
Changpeng	Lin	EPFL, CH	11-23/10/23	Development of carrier multiplication matrix elements in Yambo	CNR ISM	A. Marini
Louafi	Widad	Université de Béjaïa, DZ	11/06/23 - 12/01/24	Training on Yambo code	CNR ISM	A. Marini and D. Varsano
Muralidhar	Nalabothula	University of Luxembourg, LU	12-14/12/23	Development of electron phonon features in Yambo	CNR ISM / Unimi	D. Sangalli and F. Paleari
Bonacci	Miki	PSI Paul Scherrer Institut, CH	18-22/12/23	Development of Aiida-Yambo workflows	CNR Nano	D. Varsano and F. Paleari
Myrta	Gruning	Queen's University, Belfast, UK	20/12/2023	Planning Yambo developments	CNR ISM / Unimi	D. Sangalli
Lokamani	Mani	Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, DE	01/04 - 30/06/23	Training on FLEUR, AiiDA for high-throughput investigations of non-vdW 2D materials	FZJ	S. Blügel
Deinhart	Victor	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, DE	01/02 - 31/07/23	Training, Calculation of magnetic interaction parameters for spin-lattice models of antiferromagnets with FLEUR, AiiDA	FZJ	S. Blügel
Zong	Shuotong	Taiyuan	11/02 -	Training, Calculation of	FZJ	S. Blügel

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Dates	Topic	MaX hosting unit	Host
		University of Science and Technology, CN	01/11/23	magnetic 2D heterostructures with FLEUR		
Kawakami	Tappei	Tohoku University, JP	17/04 - 20/10/23	Training, Calculation of Fermi surface properties of 2D materials with FLEUR	FZJ	S. Blügel
Blanco-Rey	Maria	University of the Basque Country, ES	28/02 - 29/04/23	Study of electronic correlation of 1D magnetic transition metal oxides on metals using occupation control in the LDA+U formalism with FLEUR	FZJ	S. Blügel
Silvetti	Martino	Université Aix-Marseille, FR	02/12/23 - 03/01/24	Development of Yambopy	CNR Nano	F. Paleari
Rossi	Giacomo	Intel, IT	18/01/2024	Porting Yambo	CNR Nano	A. Ferretti and Yambo team
Junqueira Caldas	Marilia	Universidade de São Paulo, BR	22/01 - 01/02/24	Electronic and optical properties of defects in oxides	CNR Nano	E. Molinari
Cervantes Villanueva	Jorge	University of Valencia, SP	20/05 - 28/06/24	Training, code development, modelling new quantum states in 2D materials	CNR ISM / Unimi	D. Sangalli
Saito	Hiroto	Tohoku University, JP	10/06 - 09/08/24	Training, Calculation of response properties with FLEUR and Wannier90	FZJ	S. Blügel
Paul	Souvik	IISER Thiruvananthapuram, IN	15/06 - 07/07/24	Training, Calculation of electronic and magnetic properties of the FeSi (110) surface with FLEUR	FZJ	S. Blügel
Tas	Murat	Gebze Technical University, TR	30/06 - 28/09/24	Training, Calculation of the magnon spectrum of MnTe with FLEUR-Spex	FZJ	S. Blügel

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Dates	Topic	MaX hosting unit	Host
Han	Guihyun	University of Ulsan, KR	04/01/24 - 29/03/25	Investigation of electronic and magnetic properties of altermagnets with FLEUR	FZJ	S. Blügel
Saito	Harutaka	Osaka University, JP	10/10 - 27/12/24	Training, Calculation of hyperfine fields in complex Fe compounds with FLEUR	FZJ	S. Blügel
Ahuja	Garima	JNCASR, Jakkur, Bangalore, IN	01/09 - 26/11/24	Training, Calculation of the g-tensor with FLEUR and Wannier90	FZJ	S. Blügel
Dawson	William	RIKEN-CCS, Kobe, JP	11/11 - 04/12/24	Interoperable Workflows on Hybrid Supercomputers	CEA	L. Genovese
Dias da Silva	Gabriela	Universidade Estadual Paulista, BR	01/03/23 - 29/02/24	Training. Electrochemistry: quantum capacitance using gold/peptides interfaces.	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Cole	Ivan	RMIT University, AUS	21/06 - 31/10/23	Electrochemistry	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Fernández-Serra	Mariví	Stony Brook University, USA	17/05 - 08/06/24	Machine Learning	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Cole	Ivan	RMIT University, AUS	05/06 - 07/07/24	Electrochemistry	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Patel	Milan	RMIT University, AUS	05/06 - 07/07/24	Electrochemistry	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Cunha	Débora	Universidade Federal do ABC, BR	27/09 - 31/10/24	Training (Siesta and QM/MM). Optical properties of molecules for sola cell applications.	ICN2	P. Ordejón
de Moraes	Elizane Egífenia	Universidade Federal da	01/09/24 - 31/08/25	Training (Siesta QM/MM) and graphene-based device design	ICN2	P. Ordejón

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Dates	Topic	MaX hosting unit	Host
		Bahia, BR				
Masaki	Ryota	University of Tokyo, RIKEN, Japan	10/09/24 - 21/10/24	Training, code development, magnetic symmetry implementation	SISSA	S. Baroni

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Annex 4: List of PhD Students in MaX Labs Working on MaX Codes

Surname	Name	Affiliation	Start and final dates	Topic related with MaX	MaX hosting unit	Supervisors
Castellucci	Francesco Cosimo	Università Modena e Reggio Emilia, IT	2024-2027	Machine Learning methods in Many Body Calculations with Yambo code	CNR	E. Molinari, A. Ferretti, and D. Varsano
Petru	Milev	Università di Milano, IT	2024-2027	Coupled electron-ion Ehrenfest dynamics in Many body perturbation theory (Implementation in Yambo code)	CNR	D. Sangalli
D'Alessio	Matteo	Università Modena e Reggio Emilia, IT	2022-2025	Excitonic properties of TMD bilayers. Intensive calculations in HPC with QE and Yambo	CNR	E. Moliari and D. Varsano
Vacondio	Simone	Università Modena e Reggio Emilia, IT	2019-2023	Advanced Self Energies in atomic systems	CNR	A. Ferretti, A. Ruini, and D. Varsano
Zanfrognini	Matteo	Università Modena e Reggio Emilia, IT	2019-2022	Excitonic properties of low dimensional materials. Intensive calculations in HPC with QE and Yambo and advanced workflow creation.	CNR	E. Molinari and D. Varsano
Carbone	Johanna Paulina	RWTH Aachen, DE	2020-2023	Non-trivial Magnetization Textures in 2D-Materials involving Rare Earths. Extensive use of Fleur code	FZJ	S. Blügel
Mazhjo	Donya	RWTH Aachen, DE	2020-2023	Ab-initio investigations of spin-orbit functionalized graphene. Extensive use of Fleur code	FZJ	S. Blügel
Hilgers	Robin	RWTH Aachen, DE	2020-2023	Prediction of magnetic materials for energy and information combining data-analytics and first-principles	FZJ	S. Blügel

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Start and final dates	Topic related with MaX	MaX hosting unit	Supervisors
				theory. Extensive use of Fleur code and workflow with Aida		
Neukirchen	Alexander	RWTH Aachen, DE	2020-2023	Phonon-magnon scattering in the FLAPW method via density-functional perturbation theory. FLEUR development on Phonons with DFPT, calculations	FZJ	S. Blügel
Mahmoud	Zeer	RWTH Aachen, DE	2021-2024	First-principles study of spin-orbitronics and topological effects in transition-metal dichalcogenides. Extensive use of Fleur code	FZJ	S. Blügel
Beida	Wejdan	RWTH Aachen, DE	2022-2026	The role of non-local Coulomb interaction in 2D covalently bonded materials. FLEUR development on LDA+U+V, calculations	FZJ	S. Blügel
Bornhake	Thomas	RWTH Aachen, DE	2023-2026	First-Principles understanding of electron-magnon interactions at Interfaces and 2D-heterostructures. FLEUR development on Phonons with DFPT and electron-phonon interaction, calculation	FZJ	S. Blügel
Gašparič	Lea	Jožef Stefan Institute, SI	2021-2025	Computational insights into dry reforming of methane and hydrogen evolution reactions	IJS	A. Kokalj
Gregori	Erik	Jožef Stefan Institute, SI	2021-2025	The effect of N and Sazole molecules on corrosion inhibition: DFT analysis	IJS	A. Kokalj
Zhang	Lin	Jožef Stefan	2024-2028	Atomistic modeling of transition-metal X-ides as catalyst	IJS	A. Kokalj

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Start and final dates	Topic related with MaX	MaX hosting unit	Supervisors
		Institute, SI		materials for water electrolysis		
Podlipnik	Ivana	Jožef Stefan Institute, SI	2024-2028	Development and testing of an on-the-fly kinetic Monte Carlo computational framework	IJS	M. Poberžnik
Bastonero	Lorenzo	Univ. of Bremen, DE	2021-2024	Automated infrared and Raman spectroscopy	UBremen	N. Marzari
Wittemeier	Nils	ICN2, ES	2018-2023	First-Principles Computational Methods for Quantum Materials	ICN2	P. Ordejón and Z. Zanolli
You	Jinxuan	ICN2, ES	2019-2024	Enhancing topological properties in TMDs by proximity interaction	ICN2	P. Ordejón, M. García-Mota, and Z. Zanolli
Medondjio	Linda Sheila	ICN2, ES	2019-2025	First-principles simulations of amorphous GeSe compounds for memory selectors	ICN2	R.Farris and P. Ordejón
Jia	Jiahui	ICMAB and ICN2, ES	2020-2023	Defect and strain engineering for modulating structure and magnetism in perovskites	ICN2	M. Pruneda and G. Herranz
Febrer Calabozo	Pol	ICN2, ES	2020-2024	New techniques to simulate electrified solid-liquid interfaces better and faster	ICN2	P. Ordejón and M. Pruneda
Castillo Robles	José María	ICN2 and RMIT, ES	2020-2024	Advanced Corrosion Modelling: an atomistic approach to describe the corrosion inhibition process	ICN2	E. de Freitas, I. Cole, and P. Ordejón
Morgan	Michael Thomas	RMIT, ES	2023-	Computational Modeling of Recycled Aluminium Alloys for Corrosion Prevention in Steel: A Density Functional Theory Approach	ICN2	E. de Freitas, I. Cole, and P. Ordejón
Iqbal	Mazhar	ICN2, ES	2023-	Atomistic modeling of corrosion	ICN2	E. de Freitas, I.

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Surname	Name	Affiliation	Start and final dates	Topic related with MaX	MaX hosting unit	Supervisors
				inhibition: the role of oxides		Cole, and P. Ordejón
Navarro Rodríguez	Sara	ICN2, ES	2024-	Electrochemistry from First Principles: Electrolyte Dynamics and Chemical Reactions on Electrified Interfaces	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Radermacher	Christian	ICN2, ES	2024-	Development of advanced simulation methods based on Density Functional Theory	ICN2	P. Ordejón
Malosso	Cesare	SISSAT, IT	2020-2024	Dielectric and dynamical properties of supercooled water	SISSA	S. Baroni
Drigo	Enrico	SISSAT, IT	2020-2024	Thermoelectric effects in polar liquids and ionic conductors	SISSA	S. Baroni
Fiorentino	Alfredo	SISSAT, IT	2020-2024	Advances in lattice thermal transport in crystals and glasses	SISSA	S. Baroni
Gong	Xuenjun	SISSAT, IT	2020-2024	Ab initio thermoelasticity of crystals at extremes	SISSA	A. Dal Corso